

Nenad Ninković

Department of History, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Novi Sad
Dr Zorana Đinđića 2, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia
E-mail: nenad.ninkovic@ff.uns.ac.rs

Goran Vasin

Department of History, Faculty of Philosophy, University of Novi Sad
Dr Zorana Đinđića 2, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia
E-mail: goran.vasin@ff.uns.ac.rs

THE ARCHBISHOPRIC OF KARLOVAC IN THE SERVICE OF HEALTH – PLAGUE EPIDEMIC IN SYRMIA 1795–1796

Abstract: The plague which led to a high mortality rate and left severe consequences in Syrmia during the second half of 1795 and the beginning of 1796 is not a topic unknown in historiography. It was studied on the basis of reports sent by the Health Commission to various state institutions, but also from memoirs. A particularly important place here belongs to the description of the epidemic by Franz von Schraud, who was sent to Syrmia as a doctor precisely because of the plague. Researchers also touched on the role of the Archbishopric of Karlovac, primarily through several epistles of archbishop Stefan Stratimirović, which were published in 1940. However, an entire corpus of documents remained unknown, although it provides a picture of the events. This historical material was created as a consequence of the fact that the archbishop was not present at his headquarters (Sremski Karlovci) during the plague epidemic, so the archimandrite of the Grgeteg monastery – Stefan Avakumović, and the protopresbyter from Sremska Mitrovica – Gavrilo Isaković regularly informed him about the situation in Syrmia and their activities. Additional importance to this material is given by the fact that Avakumović was part of the escort of the royal commissioner sent to Syrmia due to the plague – first baron Pichler, and then baron Lovas. With them, he visited all places in the Syrmia County with infected people, but also the ones in their vicinity where the infection was not transmitted. During that time, Isaković was entrusted with the management of all Orthodox faithful in the Petrovaradin Regiment of the

Military Frontier, which Avakumović did not enter. Their letters show how the church was organized with the mission of preventing the spread of the epidemic; all orders of the Health Commission were published through it, because priests could reach all residents easily and they were the only ones who knew them personally. The Church accompanied all state orders with its comments, in order to convince the people that changes in liturgical and funeral practices are not in conflict with the Orthodox teaching and thus facilitate their acceptance. The paper also points out how the church helped the population and the Syrmia County economically, but also documents what abuses existed, both by the County and by the population in the vicinity of the Syrmia monasteries. The material on the basis of which the work was written is located in the Archives of SANU in Sremski Karlovci.

Keywords: plague, quarantine

Non MeSH: Syrmia, Archbishopric of Karlovac, Stefan Avakumović, Stefan Stratimirović

Throughout history, the plague has left a great inprint on human society. There are several known epidemics of this disease in Europe, which killed thousands of people, such as the Black Death in the middle of the 14th century. There were epidemics that affected, as mentioned, the entire continent, but also those that affected only certain countries or its regions. Such occurrences happened in the Habsburg monarchy as well. That is why during the 18th century decrees and laws were passed that were supposed to prevent the spread of the plague. They gave good results, so that the plague's tragic harvest was less frequent and less intense. [1, p323-27] The last epidemic occurred in the south of the Habsburg Monarchy, in Syrmia in 1795-1796. There were no major consequences for the state, because this time the outbreak was contained in Syrmia County, but it was nonetheless a traumatic experience for the local Serbian population, which for decades remembered the bitter fate and great mortality of the inhabitants of the town of Irig or its surroundings. [2, p279-85]

The plague was transferred in July 1795 from the Ottoman Empire to the Syrmia County (Provincial), to the rich town of Irig. It quickly spread to the surrounding villages and killed a large number of people in the following months. The easy spread was a consequence, on the one hand, of the failure of local government representatives and doctors, and on the other hand, due to funeral rituals, bathing of the deceased and their kissing, along with the custom of sharing the deceased's belongings. [3] The protopresbyter of Zemun, Mihajlo Pejić, was with his family in Irig at the time of the outbreak of the epidemic and has heard from acquaintances even before doctors did, that the plague had occurred and that the residents were very upset. He immediately informed the vice district chief (vice-solgabirov) Antonio Poljak and the sub-prefect of Syrmia, Janković, who replied: "You are a smart man, silence that rebellion, it is not a plague, but people were hungry, and now that they have grain they bake bread and eat it hot, after which they drink cold water and then a rotten fever from which

they die in vain occurs". [4] Janković's position was also confirmed by the county surgeon Riffel, but they could not soothe protopresbyter Pejić. He therefore made excerpts from the protocols of the dead of three Irig churches and showed that the number of dead (28 people in 18 days) was unusually high for that time of year. Janković and Poljak still did not believe that it was the plague, but during their passing through Irig, they ordered the town drummer to announce to the people not to eat hot bread and not to drink cold water. A few days later, on August 4, 1795, Dr. Andras Budai, sent from Buda to Irig, determined that it indeed was a plague, after which the settlement was ordered to be closed, separated from the surrounding area by a 2.32-meter-wide and deep moat, with branches above the ditch. Only one gate was left in the direction of Ruma, which was controlled by the army.¹ The guards separated parts of the settlement and individual houses in which there were deaths, the facility for the reception of the sick was determined, along with a special place for the burial of the deceased. In addition to the sick, the quarantine had to be endured by the healthy as well in special facilities, in order for doctors to make sure that there is no danger of spreading the disease. In this way, in addition to Irig, other settlements where the plague appeared were quarantined: Neradin, Grgeteg, Krušedolski Prnjavor, Šatrinci, Rivica, Jazak, Veliki Radinci, Grgurevci, Bešenovo, Bešenovački Prnjavor, Kamenica and Vukovar. In addition, nearby settlements, in which there was no plague, were also isolated, so the entry and exit from them was not possible, except for representatives of the authorities, the church and the Health Commission. [6] Sanitary cordons were organized, quarantines (ger. Kontumaz) and guard huts were erected, and houses belonging to infected people were demolished, burned or disinfected. In order to facilitate the work of all state bodies in preventing the spread of the epidemic, a special royal commissioner, baron Josef Pichler, was appointed. [7, 8]

Initially, there was resistance to patients being transferred to special buildings. That is why the sick went outside the houses, were left to themselves and died in vineyards, forests, gardens. They were buried only when their bodies were found, at the place where they were found, in inappropriate, often shallow graves, without informing doctors or government officials. People refused any work with the sick out of fear, including even the construction of the quarantines, but they found it difficult to give up funeral rituals, because they considered it a great sin. The deadline for burial, which was 48 hours, was not respected, so there were examples of the deceased being left unburied for eight days. Precisely because the state or local administration could not sufficiently control the population and reach every individual, baron Pichler addressed the archbishop of Karlovac, Stefan Stratimirović, to influence the dissemination of orders of the Health Commission through priests. [9] This was all the more necessary because the seat of the Archbishopric of Karlovac itself was in Sirmia, not far from the area affected by the plague. [10, 11]

¹ At that time, Pejić and his wife were in the Hopovo monastery, which was also closed, so he could not leave it. While he was staying in Irig, his mother, sister, sister's two children, maids and three servants died of the plague. He later testified at the request of Royal Commissioner Sigismund Lovas in the trial against sub-prefect Janković about his irresponsible behavior that led to the spread of the plague. [5, 6]

Stefan Stratimirović showed a high degree of cooperation with baron Pichler and all institutions that worked on preventing the plague. [12] He did not do that directly, because at the time of the outbreak, he was on the Dalj estate, and then he went to Vienna on other business, so he did not return to Sremski Karlovci until the end of the epidemic. While he was in Dalj, he managed the church and the clergy through archimandrite Stefan Avakumović from the monastery of Grgeteg. When he went to Vienna, he had to formally appoint a bishop in his stead, because the archimandrite could not perform all the functions of a bishop, including the consecration of priests. Stratimirović decided on the closest bishop, Jovan Jovanović, the bishop of Bačka, who resided in Novi Sad and only the Danube separated him from Syrmia. Jovanović did not suit baron Pichler nor archimandrite Avakumović, so his influence was quickly suppressed. [13]

Baron Pichler did not see eye to eye with the archbishop regarding bishop Jovan and did not want him in his vicinity, so he discreetly talked him out from his arrival to Syrmia – among other things, by warning that he could get infected himself and that he would have to endure quarantine. Thus, everything related to health protection was performed through correspondence with archimandrite Avakumović. [14]

At the beginning of the epidemic, the archimandrite of Grgeteg was located in the western part of Syrmia, in Vukovar and Borovo forest, and then in Ilok, near Stratimirović, but on the side of the sanitary cordon where he did not have to be in the quarantine. Fearing that he himself would be infected, which can be easily seen in his letters, Avakumović tried to leave Syrmia. [15] Although Avakumović wanted to be in Privina Glava, the baron insisted on staying with him in Ilok. There he received financial help and the opportunity to prove himself as a zealous clergyman in Pichler's service. Three years later, this helped him become the bishop of Gornji Karlovac. [16, 17]

Avakumović began his activity on August 15, 1795, when he sent an order to priests to close churches and not to bring the dead into them, and then prohibiting the kissing of the deceased, who had to be carried in closed caskets, in accordance with health regulations. Ten days later (August 25, 1795), he sent a new order that the deceased must not be escorted to the cemetery, but taken from home to the cemetery in a closed coffin and buried without any ritual. Then followed the order that priests must not visit the sick, except when they receive communion on their deathbed, and even then only with the permission of the district government representative (solgabirov) or doctors. During confession and communion, they were not allowed to come into contact with the patient, but they did everything at a distance. They administered communion using wooden utensils, i.e. spoon tied to a stick. They burned all this immediately after the communion. [18]

Fearing that the plague would enter the monasteries, on September 5, 1795, Avakumović ordered the abbots and archimandrites to close the monasteries and not to let anyone into the church except the fraternity, and only under the condition they were healthy. Each monastery that had a rural parish nearby was supposed to appoint a monk, who would serve the liturgy under the open sky, and in the case of communion, to observe the already issued orders on physical distance and burning utensils. That Stratimirović and Avakumović were serious about these orders can be seen by the

fact that Avakumović punished the abbot of the Jazak monastery, Vikentije Pajić, who went out of the monastery without permission and crossed the sanitary cordon, which was considered a criminal act. On September 17, 1795, Avakumović sentenced him to a month of monastic imprisonment on water and bread. [24, 7]

On September 28, 1795, the burial order was extended to those settlements in Srem that were not affected by the plague so far. The Health Commission, through Avakumović, sent printed rules of conduct to clergy during the plague, about which they taught their flock in the streets and yards. During that time, emphasis was placed on the explanations that the closure of churches in the circumstances of the epidemic was not against God's rules. In order not to leave the faithful without worship, Avakumović ordered that on November 8, 1795, priests could serve in churches without the presence of believers, to whom he recommended to pray in their homes, because they would know which part of the liturgy was going on by observing ringing of the church bells. This order referred only to the area of Sirmia County west of the Mandjelo cordon and the monastery prnjavor (prnjavor is a type of a village, which is close to a monastery).² Only when there is no threat of illness, Stratimirović announced that he would allow old people to come to a church, but on the condition that they stand at a distance from each other. [18, 19]

The priests were ordered to watch the movements of their parishioners and especially not to allow them to go outside the settlement. On October 30, 1795, baron Pichler informed Avakumović that he could announce that those priests who zealously fought against the plague would be rewarded. In addition, he prescribed (on November 15) that priests in quarantine will receive 1 forint per day, while those who lost their income due to the plague should make testimonies about it, so that everything could be compensated later. In this way, he tried to motivate the priests to work in the quarantines, because they avoided it due to possible infection. Due to the priests' fear, Avakumović had to write in a sharp tone to Stefan Kišdobranski, ordering him to go to Jazak quarantine or to send a monk from the Jazak monastery as his replacement. He sent the priest Stefan Vezilić to the Irig quarantine with the order that he must not leave it. However, the problems were not solved, because there was a famine, just like in Irig. The news about that reached through the priest the archimandrite of Grgeteg, who did not know what to do, except to accuse the Sirmia County of being late with all measures. [18, 5]

In order to prevent the mixing of the population, Avakumović wrote to the protopresbyters on November 17, 1795, in accordance with the orders of the Health Commission, that under the threat of church anathema people must not leave their houses and share things, especially if they had sick people in their homes, and to report immediately if they previously gave anything. [18]

In addition to archimandrite Avakumović, the protopresbyter of Mitrovica, Gavriilo Isaković, received a special kind of spiritual authority in the late autumn of

² The Mandjelos cordon cut Srem in two parts, from Ruma, north to the Danube. It was named after the village of Mandjelos, where the doctor and the administration of the cordon were located.

1795. The reason for this was based on the fact that Syrmia County and the Military Frontier were separated during the epidemic, i.e. it was impossible to move from one area to another, and protopresbyter Mihajlo Pejić could not return to Zemun from the closed Hopovo monastery. Thus, the administration of Gavril Isaković was extended to all settlements of the Petrovaradin Regiment, while those settlements in his protopresbyterate that were in the County were handed over to the Ruma governor Vasilije Krestić (from the Mandjelos cordon to the ridge of Fruška gora), the protopresbyter of Beočin Pavle Popović (from the ridge of Fruška gora to the Danube) and the protopresbyter of Šid (west of the Mandjelos cordon). The exceptions were Sremski Karlovci and Vukovar, which were closed and each under the administration of its protopresbyter. In accordance with the orders of the Health Commission, the Cantonal Command and the archbishop, Isaković banned gatherings and celebrations (baptismal and village celebrations, weddings, etc.), and threatened priests with loss of parishes and trial before secular courts if they did not act in accordance with this. [14, 20] After that, on November 21, 1795, he could state that everyone in the Military Frontier was healthy, but that great fear was present everywhere. [21] At that time, even letters could not be sent across the military-civilian border except when the military authorities, Avakumović and baron Pichler, were communicating with protopresbyter Isaković. [14] The protopresbyter of Mitrovica assured Stratimirović in the late autumn of 1795 that all orders in the Petrovaradin Regiment were being implemented and that there were no sick people there. The plague appeared in the military area only in Krnješevci, in 36 homes, but not a single home was left empty, while in 50 homes, thanks to the rapid introduction of strict measures, no one was infected. When the disease appeared in Veliki Radinci, with which the Military Frontier bordered, the cordon was tightly closed, so it was not passed on. [22] In the fight against the spread of the epidemic from Veliki Radinci, Isaković was assisted by Jovan Krstonošić, a priest from Kupinovo. [23]

Avakumović especially insisted that priests teach the people why the practice of kissing the deceased is disastrous and to point out that carrying the dead in open boxes and kissing them does not do the deceased any honor or benefit, but leads themselves and others and the whole country to death. On his orders, they explained to the faithful that all these actions had nothing to do with the teachings of the Orthodox Church, but that it is superstition and that the words spoken during the funeral – *Come, last osculation* – do not really mean to kiss, but are part of church chanting in memory of the deceased. Stratimirović's following order demanded that priests stand in front of the coffin when they say those words, in order to physically prevent people from approaching the deceased. The cross and icons could no longer be placed on the body of the deceased or the coffin, but on a special table where they were eventually kissed, but at a distance from the deceased. The archbishop asked the clergy to, in case that someone close to them dies, show by personal example devotion to such decisions, but also to warn the faithful that, in case the orders are disobeyed, both Stratimirović and secular authorities can punish them. Secular authorities could even relocate them to another part of the country. [24] The priests took the task seriously and only one case of burial offenses is known, but not in the plague-stricken settlement. [25]

Christmas and Easter were holidays on the occasion of which the archbishops of Karlovac addressed the faithful, and in 1795–1796 Stratimirović wrote in his epistles precisely about the plague. At the end of 1795, he recommended to the faithful to reduce their movement because that prevents the spread of the infection. In case they suspect that someone is infected, they should report it, as well as not to hide the sick in any way. He told them to be free from fear and live normally in their homes. He also pointed out the importance of a moderate life, the intake of food that cleanses the blood (wine, vinegar, salt, pepper, paprika), as opposed to the one that creates inflammation (cheese, meat, fish, bacon), which was in line with medical knowledge of the time. He advised them to drink boiled water with a small percentage of vinegar or wine added to it. They were supposed to keep the body, homes and yards as clean as possible, to disinfect them often with sunbathing and steam obtained by pouring vinegar on iron or hot stones. Warm dressing was mandatory, and parents were tasked with preventing children from playing and gathering on the street because it was a way of disease transmission. [26]

After this epistle, archimandrite Avakumović spent 18 days with baron Pichler in Mandjelos, from where they toured settlements every day (Irig, Neradin, Grgeteg, Krušedol, Grgurevce, Šatrinice, Ruma, Jazak, Bešenovo and Veliki Radinci). In each of them, Avakumović taught the people what Stratimirović wrote in the epistle. Between 200 and 300 people attended in Irig, and their knez Lazar Rakić was awarded with a golden chain for his dedication in the fight against the plague. The archimandrite noted that it was difficult to watch the people of Irig, that the settlement was deserted, and the living looked as if they had been killed. Both he and Pichler testified that the situation in the Irig quarantine was even worse. [20]

In order to ensure adherence to all measures, Stratimirović planned to send his protosyncellus Petar Jovanović Vidak to the Archdiocese as an exarch with the task of visiting all settlements and finding out from doctors and authorities whether there had been non-compliance with measures. Then he was supposed to go from house to house and speak out against non-compliance with measures. In Irig, Neradin, Grgeteg and Krušedol prnjavor, he was supposed to stay the longest and teach the people the most. [20] However, archimandrite Avakumović did not have a positive opinion of the archbishop's proposal, because he believed that the people whom he deemed as cruel and unsophisticated, could not quickly get rid of superstition, to which priests were also completely inclined. [27] There was no need for new measures, as everything he had done so far yielded good results. This was confirmed by Pichler's successor as imperial commissioner, Sigismund Lovas, in early 1796. [28]

Before the Great Lent on March 27, 1796, Avakumović sent the archbishop's order to the priests in order to influence the people to give up fasting, which would exhaust their organisms and thus make them susceptible to diseases. The priests in Irig, Neradin, Sremska Kamenica, Jazak, Bešenovo and the monasteries of Bešenovo and Grgeteg were specially ordered to absolve the faithful in advance from fasting and allow them to eat all types of food. [18]

A special type of activity of the church in Srem during the epidemic was the help that the monasteries gave in the fall of 1795, primarily in food. Krušedol distributed

the grain to the people of Prnjavor for seeds, and the Health Commission announced that everything would be paid for later. Even the monastery of Krušedol was temporarily opened, in order to encourage the economical recovery. In December 1795, other monasteries were asked for help in wine, brandy, grain, money or anything that could be used in the infected areas. [29, 30] The monastery forests also gained importance. Baron Pichler and Srem County prefect Lovrenčić asked the monastery for a certain amount of wood, promising that everything would be paid for later. The request of the Health Commission envisaged 15,000 fathoms of wood from the County and 6,000 from the monastery, for quarantines and cordons. Then, the Bešenovo monastery donated an amount of the needed wood. [31] While awaiting the archbishop's advice in terms of the demand for wood, Avakumović had already asked the monastery's trustees to let him know how much they could give. He tried to prevent all abuses, because he testified that Srem County officials used the plague in order to get rich illegally. [30] However, there was also abuse by the locals. Residents from the area of Bešenovo (villages Bešenovo, Bešenovo prnjavor and Stejanovci) illegally cut down the monastery forest and thus caused damage of about 1,000 fathoms of wood, not only for firewood, but also for the timber they sold. There was abuse in other places as well, so baron Pichler advised Avakumović to sue the County that encouraged or tolerated it, but the archimandrite wondered who would be able to conduct an investigation and pass a verdict at this time. While Avakumović received various testimonies about the abuse of the situation, baron Pichler wrote testimonies that he had nothing to do with the orders to cut forests down.³

All the measures that were introduced by the end of 1795 gave good results in the following period. The fact that the army was deployed on the cordons (Mandjelos, Danube, Irig venac, Western near Vukovar and the area of the Military Frontier) in addition to the domestic guard also contributed to calming the epidemic. Thus, at the beginning of 1796, the number of newly infected people outside quarantines was small, almost negligible. A great, often decisive, contribution to the acceptance of all the measures of the Health Commission was given by the church, i.e. archbishop Stefan Stratimirović, archimandrite Avakumović and protopresbyter of Mitrovica Isaković. At the beginning of 1796, thanks to all the regulations, the plague subsided and disappeared from Syrmia, and in the spring, the decrees on closing the settlements were slowly abolished and life returned to normal.

³ Zarija Dobrić from Ledinci and Commissioner Poljak ordered the cutting of the forest near the monasteries of Velika Remeta and Grgeteg. On that occasion, Poljak shouted to the peasants, "Cut them trees down, their monkish faith be damned, they are useless anyway." This was followed by Avakumović's comment about Dobrić: "This is gratitude that Your Excellency gets, for receiving him as a son at the table, and for our welcome reception in the monasteries. [He is a] wretched nationalist!" [20]

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